

The Morphological Response of 127 Durum Wheat (*Triticum turgidum* ssp *durum*) Genotypes against Salt Stress at Germination Stage

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Abstract

Salinity is one of the environmental problems and has adverse effects on plants. In this study, it was aimed to investigate the effects of different salt concentrations on 127 durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* ssp *durum*) genotypes at the germination stage. For this purpose, wheat seeds were germinated in Petri dishes for 12 days, and 0-50-100 and 200 mM NaCl solutions were applied. Increasing salinity caused reduction of germination, coleoptile length, shoot dry matter, and root length. The results showed increasing salinity concentrations inhibited durum wheat growth at germination stage. In the highest salt concentration C9, Akçakale-2000, and Vatan genotypes were found the most tolerant; and Zenit, Çeşit-1252, and Şölen-2002 were determined as the most sensitive genotypes; so according to these results. C9, Akçakale-2000, and Vatan genotypes are the cultivars to be advised for salty soils.

Keywords: Durum wheat, salinity, germination, coleoptile

1. Introduction

Wheat, is a primary individual of Poaceae family and this genus named 'Triticum' (Chen et al., 2020). It has three species which have different chromosome numbers: *T. monococcum* (diploid), *T. durum* (tetraploid) and (hexaploid) (Özkan and Genç, 1998). It is a fundamental cereal crop for many people since it provides protein and carbohydrates (Talaat and Shawky, 2014); and after maize, wheat is the second most grown cereal crop (Datta et al., 2009). Durum wheat which evolved from a wild tetraploid species of *Triticum* (*T. dicoccoides*), is the main raw material of pasta, bulgur, couscous and semolina (Bouthour et al., 2015; Kadkol and Sissons, 2016). It is a traditional Mediterranean crop and originated in the Fertile Crescent (Soriano et al., 2016). Plants are important organisms due to their sunlight conversion ability to chemical energy. Optimum environmental conditions are necessary for taking maximum yield from plants. However, plants usually under the influence of different negative exogenous factors named 'stress'. Stress factors affect wheat plants in different ways; for example heat stress decreases its productivity (Poudel et al., 2021), drought stress causes oxidative damage (Naz et al., 2021) and cadmium stress reduces the growth and pigment content (Liu et al., 2021). Also because of climate change and lack of precipitation salinity is becoming an important stress factor, which affects durum wheat, too (Soni et al., 2021a). Salinity is a major stress factor and an example of chemical stress that limits germination, growth, and productivity of plants (Sairam et al., 2002; Talaat and Shawky, 2014; Saleh and Madany, 2015). According to FAO Soil Portal data, 397.1 hectare of Earth lands (means 3,1%) is salty. Salinity means the high concentration of soluble salts. Soils, of which conductivity higher than four dS/m, classified as 'salty' and this value equals 40 mM sodium chloride (NaCl) that creates 0,2 MPa osmotic pressure (Munns and Tester, 2008, USDA-ARS, 2008). When salinity

exceeds this value and soil pH higher than 8.5, productivity begins decreasing (Sairam et al., 2002). The paucity of precipitation, excessive irrigation, and applied fertilizers are the main factors of salinity (Tester and Davenport, 2003; Radhakrishnan and Lee, 2015). Salinity tolerance shows the difference among plants. For example, paddy (*Oryza sativa*) is the most sensitive cereal while barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) is the most tolerant among cereals. Breadwheat (*Triticum aestivum*) is mid tolerant nevertheless durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum ssp. durum*)'s tolerance is less than bread wheat. Halophyte monocotyledon and relative of wheat *Agropyron elegantum* is one of the most tolerant plants against salt as it maintains life at salt concentrations like seawater (Munns et al., 2008). Salinity caused membrane disruption, decreasing soluble sugar concentration, and increasing proline, protein, root-shoot Na/K rate and antioxidative enzyme (SOD, CAT, POX and APX) activities in durum wheat genotypes (Soni et al., 2021b). Also, Bouthour et al (2015) found that salinity caused growth inhibition and decreasing chlorophyll content in two different durum wheat cultivars. This paper reports a salinity evaluation of durum wheat genotypes from different groups. The scopes of this paper are 1) to research the impact of salinity on wheat genotypes at germination and first twelve days of vegetative stage, 2) to select sensitive and tolerant genotypes of groups against salinity.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plant materials

A collection of one hundred and twenty seven *Triticum turgidum ssp. durum* genotypes and cultivars from different groups (Turkish 50; foreign 20; genebank 43 and growing 14 genotypes; given in addition file) was used in this study. The seeds of genotypes were obtained Cukurova University Department of Field Crops.

2.2 Germination and salt applications

The experiments were conducted at controlled environmental conditions in Plant Physiology Laboratory, Department of Biology, Çukurova University, in 2016. Surface sterilisation of the seeds were done with 5% commercial sodium hypochlorite solution for ten minutes and rinsed with distilled water (Kamran et al.,2009).25 seeds of each genotype were placed between moist general purposed filter papers in a glass Petri dish (90 mm*20 mm). The seeds were treated with 0 (as control, only distilled water)- 50-100 and 200 mM NaCl. The electrical conductivity of distilled water, 50-100 and 200 mM NaCl solutions suspended to 168.9 μ S/cm, 4.93 mS/cm, 9.46 mS/cm ve 17.88 mS/cm, in turn.. Petri dishes were kept under dark conditions first three days, later at 24/20 \pm 2°C day/night tempetarute, 16/8 light/dark photoperiod (Bouthour et al.,2015), and 60 \pm 5% humidity, in a controlled climate room. After three days of sowing, the seedlings of which both-radicula and plumula lengths reached 2 mm were counted as germinated (Ehtaiwesh,2016). Also coleoptile lengths of randomly selected five seedlings from each petri were measured with a ruler. Seedlings were harvested twelve days later of sowing. Four seedlings were randomly selected from each petri, then their root-shoot length and fresh weights were measured. Following these, all samples were dried in an oven at 65°C until constant dry weight (Kamran et al.,2009) and data were recorded. Germination rate (percentage) of the seeds was calculated

according to the following formula (Çarpıcı et al.,2009). Germination percentage (%) = (Number of germinated seeds/number of total seeds) * 100

2.3. Analysis of Data

Data wereevaluated with STAR statistic programme (Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research; Gulles et al.,2014) and variance analysis was done. Also, to evaluate the effects of salinity on durum wheat cultivars, rating method of Turan (2012) was used with some modifications. For this purpose, the percent change between the highest salinity concentration and control values was calculated. The genotype which had the highest percent change was scored with the lowest point 1. Also the genotype that had the lowest percent change was scored with the highest point 127 (due to 127 genotype). This calculation was done for germination rate, coleoptile length, root length and shoot dry matter parameters and then whole points of genotypes were added. Finally, the genotypes which had high points were accepted as resistant and the genotypes had low points accepted as sensitive.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the variance analysis of the germination rate of 127 durum wheat genotypes grown in different salt concentrations in petri dishes are given at Table 1. According to this, the interaction of salt concentration, genotype, salt concentration x genotypewas found significant at p<0.01significance level.

Table 1. Analysis of variance for effect genotypes and salt concentrations on germination rates of 127 durum wheat genotypes

Source	Germination Rate			
	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F value
Salt concentration	3	20769,0	6923,0	73,4**
Error (a)	12	1131,3	94,3	
Genotype	126	160039,2	1270,2	15,5**
Salt concentrationx genotype	378	46956,0	124,2	1,5**
Error (b)	1512	124312,7	82,2	
Total	2031	353208,2		

DF: Dergee of freedom; * and ** significant at 5% and 1%, respectively.

Germination rates of the whole genotypes are shown at the Table 5 and it is seen that the germination rate decreases with the increasing salt concentrations. Feghhenabi et al. (2020) declared similar results to our study by applying different concentrations of salt solutions by diluting the salty lake water to the seeds of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) and found that the germination percentage decreased with increasing salinity. Mean germination rates were found 83.6% at control plants, 81.7% at 50 mM, 80.2% at 100 mM and 75% at 200 mM salinity concentrations. Zhang et al.(2013), found the lowest germination rates of different oat (*Avena sativa* L.) cultivars against different salinity concentrations in the highest salt concentration. In addition, as seen in Table 5, the highest germination rate in the control application (0 mM salt) was in Dumlupınar (Genotype No 7) and Balcalı 85 (GN 16) genotypes, in the Dumlupınar

genotype with 50 and 100 mM salt application, the highest concentration was at 200 mM, it was detected in the Kurtulan (GN119) genotype. The lowest germination rates were determined in control, Gökgöl 79 (G.N.38) in 50 mM salt application, Inbar (G.N.63) in 100 mM salt application and Gökgöl 79 (G.N.38) genotype with the highest concentration of 200 mM salt application. When genotype groups (Turkish, foreign, genebank and growing genotypes) were examined, it was found that the groups showed a similar tendency to increase salt concentration. The mean germination of the groups at whole concentrations are seen at Figure 1. Also, the % change of the highest salt concentration compared to the control is shown in the figure. A decrease was found 9% in Turkish genotypes; while 11% was found at other three genotypes.

Figure 1. The effects of salt concentrations on different groups' germination rates (the numbers represents % change of the highest salt concentration compared to the control)

Seed germination and early seedling growth were declared as important stages in the plant lifecycle, and have been stated to affect the yield (Ahammed,2020). These stages have also been stated as the most sensitive to salinity. Delay or inhibition of the germination with salinity were attributed to the reduction in water

availability, the changes at transport of stored products and structural adjustment of proteins (Ibrahim, 2016). The variance analysis showed that, the interaction of salt concentration, genotype, salt concentration x genotype was found significant at $p < 0.01$ importance level (Table 2) for coleoptil length parameter.

Table 2. Analysis of variance for effect genotypes and salt concentrations on coleoptile lengths of 127 durum wheat genotypes

Source	Coleoptile length			
	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F value
Salt concentration	3	416847,2	138949,1	3212,8**
Error (a)	16	692,0	43,2	
Genotype	126	181494,7	1440,4	28,1**
Salt concentration x genotype	378	58307,2	154,3	3,0**
Error (b)	2016	103244,8	51,2	
Total	2539	760585,9		

DF: Dergee of freedom; * and ** significant at 5% and 1%, respectively.

Mean coleoptile lengths of whole durum wheat genotypes are given in the Table 5. Average coleoptile length of control plants was found 59 mm; also respectively 55, 45 and 26mm at increasing salinity concentrations. Similar results were found in Öner and Kırılı (2018)’s study. Coleoptile length of different wheat varieties (*Triticum aestivum* L.) showed a decreasing trend in increasing salinity concentrations and the lowest coleoptile length was found in the highest salt test in all varieties. The highest coleoptile length in control plants was determined in TR 81284 –Ankara (G.N.104) genotype (shown in Table 5); also in TR 47949 –Kars (G.N.84), TR 31902 –Malatya (G.N.99) and Menceki (G.N.115) genotypes with salinity

applications (50-100 and 200 mM). The lowest coleoptile length in control application was measured in Gap (G.N.45); in 50 mM salinity in Güney yıldızı (G.N.32), in 100 mM and 200 salinity concentrations in Dumlupınar (G.N.7) genotypes. It is reported that coleoptile elongation was inhibited against salinity as a result of the application of 100 mM NaCl to two different bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) varieties, and coleoptile length could be used in determining salt-tolerant varieties (Fang et al.,2010). When genotype groups were evaluated, four groups have had approximate values. In the highest salinity concentration, Turkish cultivars decreased coleoptil length 59% and affected more than others, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The effects of salt concentrations on different groups’ coleoptile lengths (the numbers represents % change of the highest salt concentration compared to the control)

Satish et al. (2016) examined the histochemical structure of the finger millet (*Eleusine coracana* (L.) Gaertn) coleoptyl belonging to the Poaceae family in response to salinity, and it was reported that the leaf water potential decreases against increasing salt concentrations, and the increased lignin accumulation in the cells may cause changes in the cell wall, also this situation may cause changes in the cell elongation, as a result of these may lead to morphological

changes. Considering that these morphological changes may affect length firstly, so decrease in coleoptile height can be attributed to these cellular changes. Variance analysis of the durum wheat genotypes' shoot dry matter of is shown in Table 3. With reference to this table, the interaction of salt concentration, genotype, salt concentration x genotype was found significant at $p < 0.01$ importance level.

Table 3. Analysis of variance for effect genotypes and salt concentrations on shoot dry weights of 127 durum wheat genotypes

Source	Shoot dry weight			
	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F value
Salt concentration	3	386587,6	128862,5	395,5 **
Error (a)	12	3910,0	325,8	
Genotype	126	467411,8	3709,6	24,4**
Salt concentration x genotype	378	132375,8	352,2	2,3**
Error (b)	1512	230331,9	152,3	
Total	2031	1220617,0		

DF: Degree of freedom; * and ** significant at 5 % and 1 %, respectively.

Durum wheat genotypes' whole mean shoot dry matter are shown in Table 5. Accordingly, mean values were found 91 mg in control plants, 95, 87 and 60 with increasing salinity. Similarly, two different research groups found an increase in shoot growth against low salt concentration (50 mM salinity) in two of three different durum wheat cultivars, and reduction in higher concentrations (Almansouri et al., 1999 and Yıldırım et al., 2015). Munns and Gilliam (2015) stated that plants make osmotic adjustments by synthesizing compounds at the cellular level to occur salt tolerance mechanism. In other words, the increase in weight against low salt concentration may be due to the genotypes' protect their turgor mechanism by synthesizing osmolyte to protect its turgor and increase their water holding capacity. In the present results, the

highest shoot dry matter was ascertained in Eminbey (G.N.10) genotype in control plants; 81381 -Sivas (G.N.79) in 50 mM salinity, Gündaş (G.N.36) and Özberk (G.N.41) in 100 and 200 mM salinity. The lowest values were found in Selçuklu 97 (G.N.24) in control application, Şölen 2002 (G.N.8) in 50 and 100 mM salinity; Meram 2002 (G.N.6), Dumlupınar (G.N.7) and Şölen 2002 (G.N.8) in 200 mM salinity. When genotype groups were examined, it was determined that the groups demonstrated similar disposition to increasing salinity. The average shoot dry weights of the groups at whole concentrations are seen at Figure 3. In the highest salinity concentration, gene bank and growing genotypes were found more tolerant with 29% decrease.

Figure 3. The effects of salt concentrations on different groups’ shoot dry weights (the numbers represents % change of the highest salt concentration compared to the control)

Hasegawa et al. (2000) expressed that, salinity may be destroyed membrane integrity and reduced photosynthesis. Photosynthesis, is an important mechanism that determines plant dry matter needs

water, so the inhibition of water uptake with salinity causes water shortage, damages photosynthesis and brings about impediments in dry matter accumulation of genotypes.

Figure 4 The effects of salt concentrations on different groups’ root lengths (the numbers represents % change of the highest salt concentration compared to the control)

The results of the variance analysis of the root lengths of durum wheat genotypes grown against salt concentrations are shown in Table 4. According to this, the interaction

of salt concentration, genotype, salt concentration x genotype was found significant at $p < 0.01$ importance level

Table 4. Analysis of variance for effect genotypes and salt concentrations on root lengths of 127 durum wheat genotypes

Source	Root length			
	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F value
Salt concentration	3	9180082,0	3060027,3	4464,9**
Error (a)	92	63051,9	685,4	
Genotype	126	6327447,0	50217,8	75,0**
Salt concentration x genotype	378	1914739,0	5065,5	7,6**
Error (b)	11592	7764353,4	669,8	
Total	12191	25249673,4		

DF: Dergee of freedom; * and ** significant at 5% and 1%, respectively.

Mean root lengths of the genotypes are given in Table 5. These averages were found 125mm in control plants, 128, 103 and 59 mm respectively increasing salinity. In like manner, Fellahi et al. (2019) showed that 50 mM salinity did not affect the root length in bread wheat varieties grown in differetn salinity concentrations in the petri dishes, however the increase in concentration gradually decreased the root length. The increase of root growth agaist

salinity applications was stated by different research teams, too (Ayed et al.,2014; Jbir et al.,2001). In the Table 5, it is clearly shown that the highest root length was detected in Karakılçık (G.N.126) in control, and İskenderiye (G.N.125) in other salinity concentrations. Also the lowest root length was measured in Aydın 93 (G.N.21) in control plants, Meram 2002 (G.N.6) in 100 mM salinity and in Dumlupınar (G.N.7) in other salinity concentrations.

Table 5 The effects of different salt concentrations on germination rates, coleoptile lengths, shoot sry weights ans root lengths of the 127 durum wheat genotypes

S.c.(mM)	Germination rate (%)				Coleoptile length (mm)				Shoot dry weight (mg)				Root length (mm)			
	0	50	100	200	0	50	100	200	0	50	100	200	0	50	100	200
G.n.	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std	m=std
1	87a±5	81a±8	87a±4	74a±10	58a±1	53a±3	40b±4	16c±3	80a±8	83a±5	62a±6	19b±2	106a±30	110a±29	66b±11	28c±7
2	87a±8	81a±5	61b±6	44c±3	51a±6	45ab±3	34b±4	11c±3	82a±14	65a±13	42b±1	11c±6	108a±20	69b±24	38c±11	16d±5
3	83a±7	74a±10	88a±7	89a±4	51a±4	49a±3	36b±3	11c±2	72a±11	73a±9	58a±17	13b±6	86a±21	83a±40	49b±10	19c±4
4	91a±4	88a±7	89a±4	85a±6	56a±3	51a±7	37b±2	13c±2	75a±16	72ab±4	52b±11	19c±7	87a±20	70a±12	40b±10	19c±5
5	94a±5	89a±5	93a±6	85a±6	62a±2	53a±3	41b±3	15c±1	78a±7	79a±16	48b±8	15c±1	117a±26	81b±16	55c±8	21d±4
6	94a±2	93a±4	91a±5	86a±11	57a±3	49a±2	29b±3	8c±1	62a±9	57a±3	40a±5	2b±0	103a±14	51b±11	29c±6	12c±3
7	97a±2	96a±3	98a±2	92a±11	49a±4	42a±3	26b±4	4c±2	60a±6	46ab±5	31b±3	2c±0	72a±13	45b±13	32b±5	11c±5
8	87ab±7	89a±6	82ab±5	72b±12	46ab±10	53a±6	34b±4	7c±1	55a±9	37ab±22	26b±6	2±0	110a±23	53b±15	37b±6	14c±6
9	80a±9	81a±5	75a±8	74a±12	53a±2	49a±5	44a±4	23b±2	113a±11	103a±19	92a±4	45b±2	110a±20	119a±32	100a±24	51b±10
10	65a±11	59ab±9	57ab±18	46ab±25	62a±8	60a±2	48b±6	25c±2	125a±14	108a±2	105a±15	50b±15	138a±34	155a±27	113b±37	59c±12
11	77a±7	76a±6	82a±4	78a±5	61a±5	54ab±3	49b±2	26c±5	106a±12	104a±5	93a±10	57b±13	101a±23	138a±29	103b±26	54c±15
12	79a±10	91a±4	89a±4	84a±6	61a±3	55ab±3	44b±5	20c±3	107a±19	100a±6	87a±11	45b±4	137a±28	134a±21	105b±16	45c±9
13	96a±3	90a±7	92a±5	86a±10	60a±4	59a±8	51a±4	25b±5	121a±7	113a±18	78b±45	64b±10	132a±31	113b±26	124ab±27	57c±11

14	91a=5	85ab=9	74b=4	77ab=5	55a=6	52ab=4	41b=1	19c=8	100a=4	106a=9	90a=10	53b=14	184a=45	187a=24	129b=28	59c=19
15	87a=9	90a=5	84a=8	92a=5	59a=4	49a=9	49a=3	31b=6	103ab=10	114a=7	88b=15	61c=10	89b=17	133a=25	89b=20	42c=10
16	97a=4	90a=5	90a=5	93a=6	56a=8	45ab=7	43b=4	23c=4	98a=10	103a=10	92a=2	52b=8	78b=14	112a=22	92b=18	44c=10
17	92a=5	92a=6	90a=11	94a=5	59a=3	51a=4	35b=3	29b=3	81ab=2	92a=8	90a=10	61b=10	102c=27	150a=23	128b=22	75d=14
18	81ab=11	84ab=3	88a=10	69b=23	49a=12	47a=5	38a=5	20b=2	78b=21	102a=16	72b=21	74b=20	118a=44	134a=27	88b=34	62c=14
19	95a=5	89a=7	82a=10	85a=6	43a=4	46a=5	38a=7	15b=3	85a=13	100a=4	83a=4	56b=7	97ab=22	112a=36	90b=24	41c=11
20	76a=11	61a=12	69a=8	63a=13	44a=6	35ab=4	31b=3	16c=14	61a=9	60a=7	78a=15	35b=6	87a=18	62b=15	65b=20	30c=6
21	78a=10	94a=5	89a=4	79a=4	45a=7	42ab=8	32b=3	18c=1	80ab=7	92a=12	98a=5	68b=7	72a=11	65a=12	58a=13	35b=6
22	95a=6	92ab=7	87ab=6	78b=8	47a=2	45a=4	38a=3	15b=3	55a=7	61a=9	69a=10	47a=7	93a=15	79a=12	58b=18	38c=6
23	66a=18	65a=9	65a=14	57a=6	43a=3	37ab=6	29b=7	16c=4	58b=11	85a=13	41b=14	35b=6	71a=11	72a=20	44b=13	37b=9
24	66ab=4	69a=13	64ab=13	51b=11	41a=6	42a=5	31a=4	11b=2	42ab=26	59a=10	54ab=2	34b=16	87a=26	63b=15	46bc=13	30c=7
25	88a=0	90a=7	81a=4	78a=10	51a=9	43a=7	40a=5	18b=2	74ab=13	89a=7	87ab=13	57b=6	95a=16	80a=18	85a=26	45b=8
26	79a=5	80a=9	82a=7	71a=11	51a=2	42ab=7	37b=4	19c=3	67ab=18	85a=16	83a=34	54ab=6	97ab=15	86ab=19	76b=21	44c=10
27	81a=11	77a=12	84a=9	70a=7	48a=9	43a=8	29b=5	16c=3	102ab=12	105a=11	100a=7	57b=19	96c=28	173a=29	131b=18	64d=19
28	93a=6	79a=9	85a=5	78a=11	57a=3	52ab=7	41b=2	14c=5	99a=16	105a=10	85a=10	49b=12	107b=18	143a=20	106b=21	64c=13
29	87a=8	78a=12	87a=7	78a=8	64a=6	61ab=4	49b=8	19c=2	98a=14	100a=6	94a=6	46b=17	100b=25	129a=28	126a=22	57c=14
30	78ab=8	87a=7	70b=24	86ab=2	57a=1	54a=4	47a=4	20b=5	101a=9	106a=5	95a=10	59b=6	127b=39	180a=27	126b=16	76c=14
31	86a=5	88a=6	88a=7	77a=4	61a=6	60a=7	46b=3	22c=2	115a=10	115a=13	100a=5	47b=19	104b=24	130a=29	94b=17	47c=9
32	89a=8	87a=2	75a=17	78a=2	48a=7	35b=5	27bc=3	23c=3	107a=15	99a=6	72b=19	68b=6	115a=31	129a=19	92b=17	61c=8
33	87a=4	82a=7	86a=5	85a=8	47a=10	45a=3	30b=6	17c=5	119a=13	111ab=17	93b=4	62c=9	154a=37	136ab=28	117b=13	65c=16
34	94a=7	93a=7	85a=4	82a=5	54a=9	49a=6	37b=7	24c=4	83ab=14	102a=8	102a=4	67b=13	148a=33	137a=28	95b=26	55c=11
35	91a=2	91a=5	98a=4	87a=11	58a=5	54a=2	48a=5	26b=6	90a=10	99a=4	93a=10	79a=7	134a=26	126a=20	102b=21	65c=19
36	79a=5	72a=16	73a=20	69a=7	49a=6	52a=6	44a=2	29b=4	110a=25	118a=24	113a=13	73b=7	105b=23	129a=38	111ab=24	74c=10
37	90a=5	94a=5	90a=7	89a=5	55a=7	52a=7	46a=4	33b=3	92ab=9	107a=7	103a=14	77b=9	128b=33	172a=25	131c=20	78c=12
38	58a=5	37b=13	66a=2	37b=12	47a=9	47a=7	37ab=11	31b=5	103a=8	109a=16	78b=22	69b=11	162a=42	152a=31	102b=30	67c=19
39	84a=9	86a=7	84a=9	79a=9	56a=5	50a=6	44a=4	23c=3	115a=5	117a=10	108a=12	76b=10	141a=36	125ab=27	116b=23	68c=15
40	83a=5	87a=7	80a=9	73a=10	54a=5	51a=7	43ab=6	33b=3	122a=7	110a=9	103ab=16	85b=17	119a=24	128a=25	110a=23	73b=16
41	84a=10	79a=12	86a=2	86a=5	55a=6	51a=5	39b=5	31b=3	120a=12	124a=7	104ab=9	95b=16	139a=36	144a=18	102b=16	53c=9
42	77a=7	89a=8	88a=5	89a=2	54a=5	51ab=4	42b=4	26c=7	118a=19	109a=4	107a=5	66b=21	137a=43	147a=21	118b=19	61c=15
43	86a=11	89a=6	86a=5	73a=9	51a=3	49ab=9	37b=3	25c=4	94ab=7	96ab=12	107a=4	81b=10	167a=39	159a=31	112b=21	62c=16
44	92ab=7	90a=4	93a=7	78a=10	53a=7	52a=6	47a=3	31b=3	86ab=5	95a=9	90ab=6	72b=7	91b=18	134a=30	118a=24	73b=14
45	74a=8	70a=15	70a=15	63a=9	40bc=10	55a=8	45ab=8	30c=3	104ab=10	122a=4	109a=4	85b=3	89c=33	131a=32	111b=18	67d=16
46	82a=8	76a=7	82ab=7	75b=10	49a=6	40a=7	41a=7	28b=2	96ab=7	101a=9	90a=10	64b=5	113b=28	101b=39	132a=24	71c=24
47	88a=0	89a=8	87a=5	83a=7	51a=8	49a=4	41a=3	29b=4	101a=7	110a=15	106a=9	73b=14	147a=31	127b=27	99c=22	62d=15
48	72a=12	66a=14	69a=2	61a=12	51a=3	53a=5	49a=5	34a=4	92ab=7	102a=10	95ab=7	73b=6	145a=35	143a=33	147a=23	96b=17
49	83a=11	85a=8	87a=8	77a=11	46a=2	43a=7	43a=4	27bc=4	100a=7	100a=13	98a=5	73b=5	141a=34	154a=26	145a=24	82b=12
50	88a=10	92a=3	84a=3	85a=6	74a=9	71a=9	58b=7	40c=5	87ab=7	94ab=5	96ab=6	73b=4	110b=20	144a=34	107b=24	77c=16
51	86a=2	88a=9	84a=7	56b=3	42a=7	36ab=9	27bc=7	6c=1	59a=7	42ab=11	38a=3	2b=0	114a=24	51b=12	35b=4	12c=4

52	83a=6	78a=12	75a=5	87a=9	58a=2	44b=5	41b=3	24c=3	101a=7	108a=14	92a=9	63b=6	87b=20	134a=30	97b=21	56c=14
53	96a=3	89a=7	86a=7	90a=2	60a=7	56a=5	39b=3	23c=4	100a=8	113a=7	102a=13	69b=9	119b=24	155a=22	119b=20	80c=12
54	92a=9	86a=8	88a=9	87a=8	57a=4	59a=5	45b=8	23c=5	112a=16	116a=11	99a=7	63b=19	120b=33	150a=25	108b=20	51c=9
55	82a=12	74a=15	86a=7	86a=12	45a=9	45a=3	37a=3	23b=2	99a=12	102a=5	93a=5	65b=14	146a=36	150a=27	125b=32	89c=12
56	81ab=7	87a=7	71ab=5	68b=10	60a=8	55a=7	52a=6	39b=7	95a=5	90a=18	96ab=13	78a=5	113a=33	116a=25	120a=26	82b=16
57	85a=5	80a=6	83a=8	90a=8	62a=8	58a=12	42b=4	32b=12	89a=8	90a=5	81a=8	53b=17	128a=30	126a=28	91b=21	76b=16
58	81a=8	78a=14	82a=7	73a=12	52a=5	61a=5	52a=11	30b=4	103a=6	106a=6	101a=10	73b=6	137a=32	121ab=28	106b=24	54c=12
59	89a=4	94a=2	85a=6	87a=5	55a=5	41b=4	41b=4	33b=6	96a=7	75a=44	90a=21	82b=6	140a=38	125ab=28	99b=18	72c=12
60	77a=5	76a=7	76a=7	78a=10	53ab=8	57a=4	42bc=6	31c=9	91ab=22	107a=12	83b=13	69b=17	144b=42	187a=38	115c=41	88d=21
61	80a=10	76a=6	77a=9	74a=5	50a=8	48ab=15	42ab=6	36b=5	105a=6	100a=42	106a=20	91a=6	138b=33	186a=34	122b=23	96c=17
62	92a=3	86a=8	92a=3	80a=9	62a=6	60a=9	51a=6	24b=5	79a=5	91a=7	76a=7	43b=4	127a=48	113ab=26	98b=17	49c=16
63	71a=11	59ab=9	55ab=14	44b=13	68a=9	66a=5	59a=7	29b=10	94a=11	93a=12	101a=22	57b=11	103a=22	92a=30	97a=15	45b=14
64	90a=8	80a=13	81a=8	86a=5	61a=7	62a=5	56a=7	26b=4	90a=9	110a=18	92a=10	66b=11	131a=36	139a=37	125a=22	59b=15
65	81a=8	52b=16	67ab=12	68ab=3	58ab=6	65a=5	51b=10	28c=4	115a=17	124a=11	106a=21	66b=12	138a=20	130ab=36	116b=28	64c=12
66	84a=12	76ab=10	79ab=13	66b=15	51ab=5	62a=6	46b=6	28c=6	89a=4	93a=10	85a=10	60b=12	118b=18	139a=22	126ab=22	71c=24
67	75a=10	67a=13	67a=8	74a=14	56ab=6	68a=4	51b=6	22c=8	94a=2	96a=22	94a=16	53b=19	144a=30	138a=22	128a=24	63b=23
68	65a=12	58ab=7	56ab=10	43b=11	52a=13	56a=12	52a=5	23b=3	102a=9	97a=13	111a=20	57b=8	130a=37	144a=31	126a=26	53b=17
69	77ab=4	82a=10	67ab=8	61b=11	58a=3	58a=3	53a=7	28b=4	102a=14	115a=9	104a=5	66b=3	158a=38	166a=33	132b=32	62c=16
70	85a=11	81a=11	81a=8	79ab=12	60a=10	60a=8	49a=9	29b=5	77a=7	88a=9	89b=12	54b=4	152a=23	141a=28	114b=24	59c=11
71	75a=13	66ab=15	62ab=10	57b=12	65a=10	62a=10	49b=12	29c=9	96a=15	107a=8	97a=13	60b=20	165a=25	148a=35	128b=27	53c=18
72	85a=6	79a=7	74a=10	72a=10	66a=6	68a=7	45b=21	24c=8	97b=6	121a=10	102ab=13	54c=2	177a=26	167a=25	128b=25	54c=10
73	90a=5	92a=3	90a=4	84a=7	66a=6	60a=3	45b=10	36b=6	87ab=5	102a=5	90ab=11	73b=15	183a=37	149b=39	125c=29	87d=32
74	91a=6	84ab=13	70b=10	78ab=11	61a=5	57a=6	55a=7	30b=5	79ab=7	89a=7	ab=11	65b=9	128a=38	129a=34	128a=25	69b=13
75	79a=13	82a=8	82a=4	76a=17	55ab=13	59a=6	47bc=12	36c=7	89a=6	70ab=40	76ab=9	61b=22	99b=50	130a=33	93bc=38	77c=23
76	83a=5	85a=11	83a=11	66b=8	65a=10	62a=5	50a=9	36b=8	77a=5	82a=21	80a=13	67ab=8	125a=36	132a=35	123a=28	81b=18
77	81a=11	82a=15	83a=5	64a=8	56a=10	54a=3	40b=6	29b=5	80ab=10	58b=31	83a=6	68ab=6	116b=31	137a=20	126ab=33	72c=18
78	91a=4	77a=5	79a=9	80a=6	61a=4	61a=7	48b=6	26c=4	75a=10	81a=7	71a=7	64a=5	162a=44	150a=31	121a=27	51b=19
79	88a=3	74ab=19	69bc=7	56c=13	52a=7	52a=9	42ab=3	26b=2	103b=18	128a=12	101b=7	74c=17	102a=28	124a=23	109b=22	54c=15
80	78a=17	73a=11	63a=12	73a=14	48b=12	63a=7	49b=6	28c=7	106a=11	110a=12	92ab=16	72b=17	114a=41	139a=34	113b=26	71c=25
81	68ab=18	83a=4	68ab=13	64b=27	56a=4	58a=3	47a=6	30b=4	92a=17	87a=5	90a=12	75a=13	135a=49	158a=38	126b=35	82c=22
82	79a=11	78a=7	77a=14	52b=28	52a=5	48ab=5	31b=5	21b=3	85a=7	97a=24	83a=6	56b=3	156a=44	160a=25	116b=30	64c=18
83	82a=8	77a=9	73a=19	83a=4	51a=6	54a=6	39b=7	22c=5	90ab=10	108a=7	85b=10	68b=10	135ab=42	143a=27	120b=25	65c=17
84	67a=12	80a=5	69a=4	77a=5	75a=11	85a=8	54b=14	33c=11	85ab=11	70bc=40	93a=5	61c=18	107a=37	117a=37	75b=28	48c=25
85	87a=9	95a=2	88a=7	87a=6	78a=9	66a=14	62a=5	38c=6	78ab=8	92a=8	101a=9	70b=6	112ab=25	123a=29	96b=29	58c=15
86	86ab=8	92a=3	81ab=8	71b=5	84a=11	83a=15	57b=11	41c=3	83ab=4	91a=6	87a=9	64b=13	128a=33	116a=29	80b=23	52c=20
87	75a=8	72a=7	71a=12	61a=11	72a=8	79a=8	60b=14	29c=8	82ab=16	76ab=12	71ab=12	57b=11	133a=30	110b=31	76c=28	37d=12
88	86a=7	79a=13	78a=7	72a=12	70a=10	57b=14	52b=18	29c=5	83a=4	86a=13	93a=9	50b=31	131a=43	127a=41	100b=28	60c=21
89	76a=9	75a=8	74a=5	68a=11	75a=8	65ab=19	56b=8	32c=2	93a=9	98a=6	96a=11	81a=3	144a=28	125ab=26	111b=21	59c=11

90	86a±10	84ab±3	75ab±4	69bc±4	71a±8	67a±5	53b±10	35c±8	85a±7	91a±17	81ab±11	60b±13	113a±24	126a±29	89b±28	61c±13
91	81a±4	86a±5	86a±5	79a±9	77a±7	67ab±18	63b±4	26c±7	99a±3	91a±42	93a±10	65b±6	136a±20	116b±27	72c±19	42d±13
92	74a±12	69a±20	80a±11	72a±6	60a±8	54ab±9	43b±12	18c±5	91ab±6	110a±13	87b±12	39c±8	89b±25	112a±29	79b±18	33c±10
93	66a±10	72a±12	66a±7	62ab±5	67a±6	69a±12	60a±6	25b±10	121a±9	125a±11	105a±7	67b±27	117a±30	118a±28	93b±24	45c±16
94	90a±10	91a±2	84a±6	79a±11	73ab±7	76a±8	64b±6	38c±6	81a±8	79a±8	85a±5	70a±17	134a±50	130a±21	125a±24	73b±24
95	81a±13	77a±6	77a±6	68a±5	87a±15	73b±15	61c±19	36d±7	87a±3	77a±2	70a±4	70a±8	90b±31	127a±26	80b±23	56c±20
96	72a±14	76a±7	70a±4	68a±5	82a±6	73a±11	55b±6	26c±2	119a±14	106a±10	107a±13	77b±13	120a±23	132a±19	116a±23	62b±14
97	77a±9	77a±5	72a±10	75a±8	66a±8	59ab±18	54b±4	33c±4	93a±19	103a±15	88ab±5	68b±9	127a±34	116a±25	94b±20	62c±13
98	72a±12	72a±8	76a±10	62a±12	87a±13	78a±5	62b±13	36c±10	80a±8	86a±8	82ab±16	65a±5	126a±32	115ab±28	96b±21	65c±22
99	84a±10	89a±4	79a±5	80a±10	64a±9	65a±6	75a±19	30b±6	75a±10	76ab±7	84a±4	63a±10	113a±30	115a±21	88b±30	53c±21
100	93a±7	84ab±17	89ab±8	75b±4	81a±11	65b±9	68b±7	21c±5	73ab±22	83a±14	80a±1	54b±14	92ab±32	104a±24	82b±21	35c±13
101	64b±9	89a±8	75ab±9	68b±10	81a±8	67b±10	54c±3	21d±3	85a±17	86a±33	72ab±10	54b±4	93a±23	99a±34	61b±32	35c±20
102	83a±4	86a±8	85a±7	86a±7	88a±7	66b±18	59b±8	28c±3	74ab±9	69ab±5	75a±7	52b±4	110a±36	109a±33	102a±27	51b±18
103	87a±2	85a±9	78a±10	77a±11	80a±11	73a±5	58b±10	24c±3	59a±3	62a±18	54a±14	43a±9	97a±29	110a±29	68b±23	42c±21
104	91a±8	90a±8	87ab±4	72b±22	94ab±11	79a±10	66b±11	34c±8	79a±14	93a±9	79a±24	49b±13	114a±35	119a±17	77b±31	39c±21
105	93a±7	91a±4	95a±5	89a±2	53a±12	56a±4	48a±9	35b±4	81ab±30	97a±7	87a±5	63b±12	109b±46	137a±28	105b±18	44c±12
106	92a±9	90a±5	90a±7	89a±2	60a±14	54ab±9	48b±5	29c±4	102a±16	121a±31	110a±12	66b±18	146a±27	146a±23	105b±18	54c±15
107	88a±9	88a±0	91a±7	88a±3	58ab±12	67a±6	48b±6	29c±7	86a±5	84a±10	79a±8	50b±7	111a±19	93a±24	95a±21	31b±11
108	93a±7	91a±8	87a±4	82a±11	64a±8	56a±14	57a±7	30b±5	79a±12	88a±11	87a±20	51b±11	138a±26	108b±25	92b±27	40c±21
109	93a±2	89a±5	92a±6	85a±2	58a±10	66a±5	42b±9	29c±6	106a±10	109a±9	97a±7	69b±15	121a±27	118a±22	102a±23	56b±16
110	81a±10	82a±8	82a±11	69a±4	63a±9	49b±13	48b±10	28c±3	102a±9	103a±13	97a±7	88b±3	138a±32	126ab±43	115b±22	52c±18
111	71a±8	70a±14	78a±10	63a±6	62a±3	58ab±12	50b±5	39c±29	102a±7	97a±3	94a±11	68b±22	137a±25	115b±35	106b±18	50c±19
112	94a±10	83a±16	89a±8	82a±10	62a±7	54ab±7	48b±5	30c±2	109a±11	105a±11	100a±11	73b±8	148a±34	116b±33	117b±16	70c±17
113	84a±3	82a±11	80a±6	63b±20	65a±4	65a±5	54a±3	40b±5	103a±9	94ab±14	104a±11	73b±6	136ab±23	152a±34	127b±41	67c±19
114	66a±11	54a±14	60a±19	52a±6	46ab±6	51a±6	37bc±10	26c±5	117a±8	118a±10	88b±18	62c±10	139a±31	130a±30	137a±39	87b±13
115	84a±10	84a±13	90a±2	75a±17	56a±10	64a±7	56a±4	42b±4	89a±5	85a±13	84a±9	75a±3	166a±46	141b±34	110c±19	55d±15
116	77a±12	56b±19	85a±7	59b±2	49a±6	43ab±5	36bc±6	29c±4	106a±2	103a±14	96a±13	69b±12	157a±33	145a±33	111b±17	67c±17
117	84a±9	81a±11	72a±10	77a±13	67a±4	50b±3	48b±6	26c±3	105a±10	112a±6	113a±10	78b±15	144ab±33	159a±35	139b±36	95c±23
118	93a±6	90a±10	85a±11	79a±11	57a±6	47ab±8	36b±4	22c±4	86a±9	83a±9	94a±6	54b±8	115b±36	154a±42	145a±22	87c±23
119	89a±7	92a±3	95a±8	95a±5	56a±4	51ab±6	40b±5	22c±2	88a±3	83a±5	83a±11	66a±4	156a±48	156a±34	125b±25	81c±18
120	93a±8	91a±4	82a±8	84a±6	52a±6	45a±3	34b±6	23b±1	84a±7	87a±3	83a±10	53b±6	149a±49	151a±27	123b±37	88c±21
121	83a±8	80a±3	62b±2	68ab±17	54a±7	43ab±5	40b±3	21c±3	76ab±6	91a±10	92a±3	65b±8	168a±30	139b±36	132b±25	75c±19
122	89a±6	90a±5	86a±7	87a±14	46a±13	38a±10	39a±5	18b±4	100a±16	97a±10	97a±7	80a±11	171a±32	157a±40	144b±26	93c±15
123	81ab±9	86a±10	72ab±15	65b±4	46a±10	41a±6	39a±14	23b±3	106a±13	100a±10	94a±9	59b±9	175a±44	152b±41	136b±29	90c±22
124	93a±7	87ab±6	89ab±4	74b±10	57a±2	46a±11	31b±5	23b±5	85ab±11	95a±6	96a±10	71b±14	184a±45	183a±30	133b±28	100c±26
125	92a±9	95a±5	94a±2	81a±5	51a±12	40ab±8	32bc±7	21c±3	104a±19	102a±19	102a±20	73b±5	133c±68	193a±37	157b±27	110d±19
126	91a±5	95a±5	93a±9	95a±6	75a±8	57b±5	49bc±11	37c±3	68ab±13	79ab±7	90a±7	59b±3	189a±30	162b±31	126c±27	97d±21
127	94ab±8	95a±6	78b±2	89ab±7	81a±9	68b±8	53c±7	37d±3	92a±6	97a±10	106a±5	67b±9	102b±28	125a±34	103b±25	72c±15

WG	83,6±11	81,7±13	80,2±12	75±15	59±13	55±13	45±12	26±9	91±19	95±22	87±20	60±21	378±113	466±154	386±146	216±94
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S.c.,Salt concentration, G.n.:Genotype number, S.d.:Standart deviation;means with the same letter in the columns do not differ significantly (p<0.01)

Similarly other three parameters, four groups have had similar averages as shown in Figure 4. According to table, gene bank genotypes affected more than others with 55% in the highest salinity.

3.1. General effect of salinity on durum wheat genotypes

The results showed that the most tolerant cultivars were found as C9 (G. N. 61,

foreign), Akçakale-2000 (G. N. 37; Turkish) and Vatan (G.N.50; Turkish) genotypes and the most sensitive ones were found Zenit (G.N.51;foreign), Çeşit-1252 (G.N.2;Turkish) and Şölen-2002 (G.N.8;Turkish) respectively, at the highest salt concentration (200 mM NaCl). Being certified of these tolerant genotypes as ‘cultivar’, may be associated of having

stress tolerance mechanisms through the breeding period. Akçakale 2000 and Vatan genotypes were also declared as having high pasta quality with their high sedimentation values (Koyuncu, 2009). In addition to these, Ay et al. (2011) declared that Şölen 2002, which is the most sensitive genotypes of the present study, was found sensitive against yellow rust and brown rust in two different researches. Another sensitive genotype, Çeşit 1252 was notified as having low pasta cooking quality and that situation was correlated with its protein quality and quantity (Bozkurt, 2012). The negative findings of these genotypes may be a response of their sensitivity against salinity.

4. Conclusions

Germination stage is an important period of plant growth. At the beginning of the study two things were aimed: to learn the effects of salinity on durum wheat genotypes' at germination stage and to select sensitive and tolerant genotypes of them. Firstly, mean comparison signed that salinity affected germination rate, coleoptile length, shoot dry weight and root length of the 127 durum wheat genotypes' negatively at germination stage. Secondly C9 (G.N.61;foreign), Akçakale-2000 (G.N.37;Turkish) and Vatan (G.N.50; Turkish) genotypes were found the most tolerant genotypes, while Zenit (G.N.51;foreign), Çeşit-1252 (G.N.2;Turkish) ve Şölen-2002 (G.N.8;Turkish) genotypes were detected as the most sensitive in 200 mM salt concentration (the highest concentration of the present study). It is suggested that the producers should prefer these tolerant genotypes and avoid sensitive ones in the salty soils. It is necessary conducting new treatments with longer period and making detailed analyses for more precise results. The tolerance mechanisms of the tolerant genotypes may be discussed by breeders to develop new tolerant cultivars.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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References

- Ahamed, G. J., Gantait, S., Mitra, M., Yang, Y., Li, X., 2020. Role of ethylene crosstalk in seed germination and early seedling development: A review. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 151:124-131.
- Almansouri, M., Kinet, J. M., Lutts, S., 2001. Effect of salt and osmotic stresses on germination in durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.). *Plant and Soil*, 231(2): 243-254.
- Anonymous, 2023. Salt affected soils. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, (<http://www.fao.org/soils-portal/soil-management/management-of-some-problem-soils/salt-affected-soils/more-information-on-salt-affected-soils/en/>). (Accessed: 20.01.2023).

- Ay, H., Mert, Z., Akan, K., 2011. Çukurova Bölgesinde Bazı Makarnalık Buğday Çeşitlerinin Sarı Pasa (*Puccinia striiformis*) Reaksiyonları. *GAP VI. Tarım Kongresi, Conference Proceedings Book*, 9-12 Mayıs, 9-12 Mayıs, Şanlıurfa, 67-72.
- Ay, H., Mert, Z., Akan, K., 2011. Çukurova Bölgesinde Bazı Makarnalık Buğday Çeşitlerinin Kahverengi Pasa (*Puccinia recondita*) Reaksiyonları. *GAP VI. Tarım Kongresi, Conference Proceedings Book*, 9-12 Mayıs, Şanlıurfa, 62-66.
- Ayed, S., Rassaa, N., Chamekh, Z., Beji, S., Karoui, F., Bouzaien, T., Mrabit, M., Ben, Y. M., 2014. Effect of salt stress (sodium chloride) on germination and seedling growth of durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.) genotypes. *International Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation*, 6(4): 320-325.
- Bouthour, D., Kalai, T., Chaffei, H. C., Goui, H., Corpas, J., 2015. Differential response of NADP-dehydrogenases and carbon metabolism in leaves and roots of two durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.) cultivars (Karim and Azizi) with different sensitivities to salt stress. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 179: p 56-63.
- Bozkurt, M., 2012. Effect of different wheat varieties on pasta quality. Ms thesis, METU Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences, Ankara.
- Carpici, E. B., Celik, N., Bayram, G., 2009. Effects of salt stress on germination of some maize (*Zea mays* L.) cultivars. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 8(19):4918-4922.
- Chen, N., Chen, W. J., Yan, H., Wang, Y., Kang, H. Y., Zhang, H. Q., Zhou, Y. H., Sun, G. L., Sha, L. N., Fan, X., 2020. Evolutionary patterns of plastome uncover diploid-polyploid maternal relationships in Triticeae. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 149: 106838.
- Datta, J. K., Nag, S., Banerjee, A., Mondal, N. K., 2009. Impact of salt stress on five varieties of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivars under laboratory condition. *Journal of Applied Science Environment Manage*, 13: p 93-97.
- Fang, W., Di, D., Pei, D., Baoshan, W., 2010. Coleoptile elongation response of different salt-tolerant wheat cultivars to NaCl stress. *Europe PMC Search life-sciences literaure*, 2053-2058.
- Feghhenabi, F., Hadi, H., Khodaverdiloo, H., Van Genuchten, M. T., 2020. Seed priming alleviated salinity stress during germination and emergence of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Agricultural Water Management*, 231, 106022.
- Fellahi, Z. E. A., Zaghdoudi, H., Bensaadi, H., Boutalbi, W., Hannachi, A., 2019. Assessment of salt stress effect on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivars at seedling stage. *Agriculturae Conspectus Scientificus*, 84(4): 347-355.
- Gulles, A. A., Bartolome, V. I., Morantte, R. I. Z. A., Nora, L. A., Relente, C. E. N., Talay, D. T., Cañeda, A., Ye, G., 2014. Randomization and analysis of data using STAR [Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research]. *Philippine Journal of Crop Science (Philippines)*.
- Hasegawa, P. M., Bressan, R. A., Zhu, J. K., Bohnert, H. J., 2000. Plant cellular and molecular responses to high salinity. *Annual review of plant biology*, 51(1): 463-499.
- Ibrahim, E. A., 2016. Seed priming to alleviate salinity stress in germinating seeds. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 192: 38-46.
- Jbir, N., Chaibi, W., Ammar, S., Jemmali, A., Ayadi, A., 2001. Root growth and lignification of two wheat species differing in their sensitivity to NaCl, in response to salt stress. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences-Series III-Sciences de la Vie*, 324(9): 863-868.
- Kadkol, G. P., Sissons, M., 2016. Durum Wheat: Overview. (Ed. Wrigley, C., Corke, H., Seetharaman, K., Faubion, J.) *Encyclopedia of Food Grains*. Elsevier Academic Press, Oxford. p.117-124.

- Kamran, M., Shahbaz, M., Ashraf, M., Akram, N. A., 2009. Alleviation of drought-induced adverse effects in spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) using proline as a pre-sowing seed treatment. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 41(2):621-632.
- Koyuncu, M., 2009. Screening of durum wheat landraces for selected traits associated with pasta quality. Ms thesis, Gaziosmanpaşa University, Institute of Science, Ankara.
- Liu, J., Gai, L., Zong, H., 2021. Foliage application of chitosan alleviates the adverse effects of cadmium stress in wheat seedlings (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 164:115-121.
- Munns, R., Tester, M., 2008. Mechanisms of Salinity Tolerance. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 59: p 651-681.
- Munns, R., Gilliam, M., 2015. Salinity tolerance of crops—what is the cost?. *New phytologist*, 208(3): 668-673.
- Naz, R., Batool, S., Shahid, M., Keyani, R., Yasmin, H., Nosheen, A., Hassan, M. N., Mumtaz, S., Siddiqui, M. H., 2021. Exogenous silicon and hydrogen sulfide alleviates the simultaneously occurring drought stress and leaf rust infection in wheat. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 166: 558-571.
- Öner, F., Kirli, A., 2018. Effects of salt stress on germination and seedling growth of different bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) cultivars. *Akademik Ziraat Dergisi*, 7(2): 191-196.
- Poudel, P. B., Poudel, M. R., Puri, R. R., 2021. Evaluation of heat stress tolerance in spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotypes using stress tolerance indices in western region of Nepal. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 5: 100179.
- Radhakrishnan, R., Lee, I. J., 2015. Penicillium–sesame interactions: A remedy for mitigating high salinity stress effects on primary and defense metabolites in plants. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 116: 47-60.
- Sairam, R. K., Rao, K. V., Srivastava, G. C., 2002. Differential response of wheat genotypes to long term salinity stress in relation oxidative stress, antioxidant activity and osmolyte concentration. *Plant Science*, 16: 1037–1046.
- Saleh, M. A., Madany, M. M. Y., 2015. Coumarin pretreatment alleviates salinity stress in wheat seedlings. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 88: 27-35.
- Satish, L., Rathinapriya, P., Rency, A. S., Ceasar, S. A., Prathibha, M., Pandian, S., Rameshkumar, R., Ramesh, M., 2016. Effect of salinity stress on finger millet (*Eleusine coracana* (L.) Gaertn): histochemical and morphological analysis of coleoptile and coleorhizae. *Flora-morphology, distribution. Functional Ecology of Plants*, 222: 111-120.
- Soni, S., Kumar, A., Sehrawat, N., Kumar, A., Kumar, N., Lata, C., Mann, A., 2021. Effect of saline irrigation on plant water traits, photosynthesis and ionic balance in durum wheat genotypes. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 28(4): 2510-2517.
- Soni, S., Kumar, A., Sehrawat, N., Kumar, N., Kaur, G., Kumar, A., Mann, A., 2021. Variability of durum wheat genotypes in terms of physio-biochemical traits against salinity stress. *Cereal Research Communications*, 49(1): 45-54.
- Soriano, J. M., Villegas, D., Aranzana, M. H., Moral, L. F. G., Royo, C., 2016. Genetic structure of modern durum wheat cultivars and Mediterranean landraces matches with their agronomic performance. *Plos One*, p:1-19.
- Talaat, N. B., Shawky, B. T., 2014. Protective effects of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) plants exposed to salinity. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 20-31.
- Tester, M., Davenport, R., 2003. Na⁺ tolerance and Na⁺ transport in higher plants. *Annals of Botany*, 91: 503–527.

Turan, Ö., 2012. Nohut çeşitlerinde düşük sıcaklığa dayanıklılığın fizyolojik, biyokimyasal ve moleküler düzeyde incelenmesi. Phd Thesis, Hacettepe University Institute of Science, Ankara.

USDA-ARS. 2008. Research Databases. Bibliography on Salt Tolerance. George E. Brown, Jr. Salinity Lab. US Dep. Agric., Agric. Res. Serv. Riverside, CA.

Yildirim, M., Kizilgeci, F., Akinci, C., Albayrak, O., 2015. Response of durum

wheat seedlings to salinity. *Notulae Botanicae Horti Agrobotanici Cluj-Napoca*, 43(1): 108-112.

Zhang, X. Q., Lu, Z. Y., Cheng, Y. C., Guo, X. X., Tian, L., Zhang, J. Z., Xian, F., He, P. C., 2013. Effects of mixed salt stress on germination percentage and protection system of oat seedling. *Advance Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 592: 197-205.

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